

Effect of a “Stochastic” Potential in Bound State Quantum Mechanics Part II

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In a previous note (1), we argued that a potential $V(x)$ might be written as:
 $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V(k) \exp(ikx)$ on physical grounds, where each $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ acts at a different time. This means portions of the $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ cancel with each other or in other words pieces of the forces associated with each $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ cancel. Thus, there is an “average” or overall $V(x)$ over time as well as an “average” kinetic energy and these satisfy conservation of energy. The various $V(k)\exp(ikx)$, however, create a momentum distribution in time at each x which depends on the form $V(k)\exp(ikx)$. In a previous note (2), we argued that $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$. Given that each $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ acts at a different time, a particle feels the kinematic effects of the full force associated with this term, even though portions of this force cancel with other k' terms. Thus, there is extra motion not associated with “average” kinetic energy or classical motion and also “fluctuation” type forces which cancel out. It appears that having $P(p/x)$ be a complex periodic probability is non-physical, but this periodic behaviour in x manifests itself in spatial density (which is an average over time), but is nevertheless considered physical. In this note, we try to investigate further this idea which was presented in (1). We think it may be good to have a picture of single particle motion in a quantum bound state in addition to the usual ensemble averages, especially since there is interest in the literature in finding “classical” (vibrating) systems which exhibit quantum-like features. Also, the ground state solution of a quantum oscillator matches the statistical features of a gas with temperature T with an oscillator potential. In statistical mechanics, one also has ensemble averages, but may consider the stochastic motion of a single particle. We argue that a similar stochastic behaviour applies to a quantum particle.

Conservation of Energy

For many classical systems, one has: Kinetic energy(x) + $V(x) = E$. If the particle is bound, it may move to the right for some time, stop, and then move to the left etc. In quantum mechanical bound systems, one uses the classical potential $V(x)$, but there is no $x(t)$, $v(t)$, $a(t)$ solution. Also, motion to the right and left is considered as all time is removed.

We thus argue that $V(x)$ is a time “averaged” potential consisting of:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V(k) \exp(ikx) \quad ((1))$$

We also argue that each addend must be physical because the periodicity of $\exp(ikx)$ leads to physically observable periodicity in spatial density in many bound systems which is a key feature of quantum mechanics. Even when high energy E quantum bound states are compared to classical systems, spatial density periodicity is present. As argued in (1), a key feature of ((1)) is the partial cancellation of different potential terms for different momenta k meaning corresponding forces partially cancel. If each addend, however, acts at a different time, force

portions which ultimately cancel may give rise to motion which is not part of the “average” classical motion associated directly with $V(x)$. For example, $-d/dx V(x)$ may have one sign, but $V(k)\exp(ikx) + V(-k)\exp(-ikx)$ may give a periodic function whose derivative $-d/dx$ is also a periodic function. Thus, the addends of ((1)) may produce forward/backward motion or at least slowing down/speeding up motion which is not directly seen in $-d/dx V(x)$. For example, consider $V(k)=V(-k)$. Then: $V(k)\exp(ikx)+V(-k)\exp(-ikx)$ is proportional to $V(k)\cos(kx)$ which is positive in some regions of x and negative in others. Thus, $-d/dx V(k)\cos(kx) = k V(k) \sin(kx)$ is also positive/negative in x meaning the average kinetic energy portions associated with $k / -k$ must increase or decrease within these regions.

In (2), we argued that $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ in ((1)) leads to $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ which also exhibits periodic behaviour for each p as can be seen by adding $P(p/x)+P(-p/x)$ (even though p and $-p$ occur at different times). One finds again $\sin(px)$ or $\cos(px)$ behaviour if $a(p)=-a(-p)$ or $a(p)=a(-p)$. Thus, averages taken at x using $P(p/x)$ may have positive or negative contributions or even vanishing contributions from $p/-p$. If one considers the change in average kinetic energy due to $p/-p$ one has for example $d/dx a(p) \cos(px) = -a(p)p \sin(px)$. Thus, p momentum conditional probability terms establish their own spatial periodic regions in which they may contribute positive or negative kinetic energy to the average in order that d/dx of $p^*p/2m P(p/x)$ yield a function which may be positive or negative corresponding to the negative or positive work of the various $V(k)\exp(ipx)$ terms.

Thus, the argument seems to be that $V(k)\sin(kx)$ or $V(k)\cos(kx)$ may perform negative or positive work in different x regions leading to positive or negative changes in kinetic energy for the $f(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ terms upon which it acts. Given that $V(k)\sin(kx)$ or $V(k)\cos(kx)$ acts on one $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ at a time, these may have a change of kinetic energy which is either positive or negative. This change, however, is obtained using $d/dx p^*p/2m a(p) \cos(px)/W(x)$ if $a(p)=a(-p)$ and one considers the average of $p/-p$ (at different times), so the contribution to average kinetic energy itself becomes positive or negative, something one does not see in classical physics.

Average Kinetic Energy

On average, conservation of energy applies at each point x . The various $V(k)\sin(kx)$ or $V(k)\cos(kx)$ terms, however, lead to increases or decreases in kinetic energy while $V(x)$ may only lead to an increase in kinetic energy for a particle moving in one direction. Thus, we argue that the periodic features of the $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ terms create periodic behaviour in the probabilities $P(p/x)$. This allows for combination $P(p/x) + P(-p/x)$ to have the form $\sin(px)$ or $\cos(px)$ which may be negative and can remove kinetic energies stirred up by $V(k)\sin(kx)$ or $V(k)\cos(kx)$ which should not be part of the average kinetic energy as argued in (1).

In other words, the entire issue of $\sin(kx)$ being negative or positive is associated with negative or positive work by $V(k)\sin(kx)$ or $V(k)\cos(kx)$. This means there may be increases or decreases in “pockets” of average kinetic energy (i.e. averages of only a few p values) from x to $x+\delta x$. A periodic change in a pocket of average kinetic energy, however, is of the form $d/dx KE$ average pocket, so this suggests that KE average pocket should be periodic itself. Thus, one may have KE average pocket <0 which is unusual. For example, for $P(p/x)=a(p) \exp(ipx)/$

$W(x)$, an average KE pocket may be created using p and $-p$ if $a(p)=a(-p)$ for example. In such a case, $P(p/x) + P(-p/x)$ is proportional to $\cos(px)$ which may be negative or positive depending on x . This issue does not disappear if one uses $P(p/x) P(x)$ instead as $P(x)$ is strictly positive (spatial density).

We try to consider this idea in more detail.

Acceleration and Momentum Transfer

The potential addends $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ are associated with forces of $-V(k) ik \exp(ikx)$, yet the “ k ” stands out as an actual momentum hit according to (2). What then does $-V(k)\exp(ikx)$, which is clearly part of the force (and part of the potential), represent? In (2) we argued that these must be linked to the probability $P(p/x)$. If one has a momentum ensemble at x with momentum p and it receives a momentum hit of “ k ”, its momentum changes to $p+k$. At the same time work occurs as average kinetic energy changes from x to $x+\delta x$. Thus, $P(p/x+\delta x)$ must differ from $P(p/x)$.

Even though, an addend force $-V(k) ik \exp(ikx)$ gives a momentum hit of k , $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ is also part of the force and must be involved in changing the probability $P(p/x)$. For example, a k_i from $V(x)$ may augment a particle with p_j such that $k_i+p_j = p$. There are many such situations and an overall coupling of the addends of ((1)) with the various ensemble probabilities seems to occur in order to create $P(p/x+\delta x)$. We have argued in (2), that $P(p/x)=a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ so that $\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x)$. Thus, the conditional probability readily couples with the potential addends or the force addends contribute to a change in $P(p/x)$ as it becomes $P(p/x+\delta x)$. We have argued above that $\exp(ikx)$ in ((1)) is based on a physical behaviour of the potential namely $\exp(ikx)$. This “physical” periodicity becomes part of the conditional probability $P(p/x)$ which in turn effects $W(x)$ and hence spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$. Thus, there are physical consequences of having $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ as a potential addend in ((1)). This physical periodicity $\exp(ikx)$ governs the physical probability of $P(p/x)$ which in turn is periodical. Thus, $P(p/x)$ may approach 0 in some x region or increase/decrease in another or even become negative. At first the negative probability seems like a problem, but it seems to follow from $\exp(ikx)V(k)$. If $V(x)$ is strictly rising i.e. $d/dx V(x)>0$, the sum of $k/-k$ may yield $\sin(kx)$ or $\cos(kx)$ which has opposite signs in different x regions, indicating that kinetic energy is being increased or decreased. For the $P(p/x)$ approach, one has an ensemble at x so the momentum p exists at each x . One may only change its conditional probability at each x . Thus, the form $a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ seems to resemble a physical behaviour in that it is driven by the potential addends $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ which are considered a priori to be physical. Thus, it is not enough that a particle with p at x receives a hit of k momentum from the force receiving a new momentum of $p+k$, its conditional probability is also altered by $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ coupling with $a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$.

What does it physically mean then to have $P(p/x) + P(-p/x)<0$? A particle may have either p or $-p$ at time t_i , thus the sum of the two probabilities which yields $\sin(px)$ or $\cos(px)$ occurs at two different times. It is an average which one may argue does not have to have physical meaning, yet average kinetic energy and $V(x)$ seem to have physical meaning as does spatial density

It should be noted that $\frac{p^2}{2m} [P(p/x) + P(-p/x)] < 0$ is associated with the idea of negative work from various $V(k)\exp(ipx)$. The confusing point is that $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ in classical physics is always positive and the overall average $\sum \frac{p^2}{2m} P(p/x) / W(x) > 0$. Nevertheless, it seems that the term $\frac{p^2}{2m} P(p/x)$ incorporates the idea of a dynamic process i.e. negative work for some x regions for $p/-p$. It should be noted that p itself represents a dynamic process in the sense that one needs velocity and this needs to be measured by finding Δx and Δt . Thus, the averages taken using $P(p/x)$ take into account the idea of dynamics with positive work done in some cases and negative in others. Thus, this is a more complicated notion of average, but one should note that the nature of $P(p/x)$ is governed directly by the form of the $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ terms.

The spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ consists of terms taken at many different times. The negative values of $\sin(px)$ and $\cos(px)$ are due to the behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$ alone as $W(x)$ may be strictly positive e.g. $W(x) = A\exp(-ax^2)$ for a ground state oscillator. This does not only affect average kinetic energy i.e. $\frac{p^2}{2m} [P(p/x) + P(-p/x)]$. When calculating spatial density, one has: $\sum_{i,j} a(p_i) \exp(ip_i x) a(p_j) \exp(ip_j x)$. If $a(p) = a(-p)$, then there will be $\cos((p_i + p_j)x)$ terms which may have positive or negative values in different x regions although $W^*(x)W(x) > 0$ at each x . How can this be? How can one have a negative partial spatial density average piece $\cos((p_i + p_j)x)$? In a previous note, we argued that a particle moving through Δx has a relative conditional probability $a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but receives a hit and changes to $a(p_2)\exp(ip_2 x)$. Thus, the relative probability for this event is $a(p)\exp(ipx)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2 x)$. All combinations need to be summed and this yields the spatial density or average. Like with average kinetic energy, the overall result is positive, but partial terms may be negative in different x regions leading to a periodic pattern. Imagine a classical particle moving at a constant speed and bouncing back and forth. It spends the same amount of time in each Δx region i.e. constant density. Alter this scenario to imagine a potential with a bound state. There is acceleration in the system and the particle spends a certain amount of time in each Δx region. Let $1/v$ proportional to the time spent in each Δx and let this be proportional to spatial density. Next, imagine a periodic perturbation changing the dynamics so the particle speeds up (spends less time) in some Δx regions and more in others at different times, but overall the potential is $V(x)$. One might argue that its average spatial density has changed due to some increases due to periodic perturbations in some areas and decreased in others. Then, consider many particles bouncing back and forth in the same way i.e. an ensemble average if you like. It will appear that some particles (or ensemble p momentum terms) have lost density and others have gained density relative to the $V(x)$ density scenario. Thus, the periodic behaviour of $V(k)\exp(ikx)$'s leads to periodic motions which may speed up or slow down particles leading to a sense of spatial density (product of relative conditional probabilities) increasing or decreasing. In other words, it is difficult to picture a negative partial average spatial density, but one may picture a density which lowers the " $V(x)$ density" in some x regions and augments it in others due to a periodic perturbation which cancels out in time. The same behaviour occurs for the wavefunction $W(x)$ except that it may be negative overall as well as having partial sums being negative.

Fourier Series

One may argue that the above is nothing more than Fourier series analysis. The fact, however, that periodicity appears in the wavefunction and carries through into the spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ suggests there is physical reality associated with this periodicity included in the Fourier $\exp(ipx)$ basis. In this note, we argue that this “reality” begins with the nature of the potential which dictates the form of the probabilities of the momentum distribution at each point x i.e. $P(p/x)$. Given that there is an ensemble, each p may exist at each x , so the probabilities govern the dynamics and there is “cancellation” of partial average density terms and partial kinetic energy density terms as well as cancellation of force terms $-d/dx V(k) \exp(ikx)$ in creating overall average densities and kinetic energy which are positive. Negative terms in a kinetic energy average are difficult to imagine unless they carry dynamical information i.e. they are negative because they are linked to negative work and only represent part of the ensemble.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ for physical reasons with each term giving a “ k ” momentum hit at a different time. This leads to a momentum distribution $P(p/x)$ at each x with weights governed by $V(k)\exp(ikx)$. In (2), we argued these weights $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. Partial sums (i.e. k and $-k$) of the addends may yield terms such as $\cos(kx)$ if $V(k) = V(-k)$. These may be positive or negative in different x regions and give rise to positive and negative forces which may slow or speed up particles. For a statistical picture, however, accelerating a particle means changing $P(p/x)$. Thus, there are different kinetic energies than expected by the sum $V(x)$ i.e. different $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ partially cancel. As a result, one expects periodic x behaviour for $P(p/x)$ which allows for “extra” kinetic energy to be removed from x i.e. p and $-p$ may yields $p^2/2m \cos(px)$ which is negative in some regions. Thus, it seems one is dealing with a new kind of average which includes dynamical effects which must cancel out when creating an average to eliminate non-average motion. This allows one to create an average such that: $\text{Sum over } p p^2/2m a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x) + V(x) = E$. At first, this may appear to be Fourier series manipulation except for the fact that $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and so exhibits periodic behaviour which carries over into the spatial density $W(x)W(x)$. The periodic features of $W(x)W(x)$, even though it is a product of an ensemble average $W(x)$ is considered to be a physical measurable (with soft measurements).

For a classical system, speeds are relatively low, distances are large and times large compared to quantum mechanical numbers. Thus, each of the $V(k)\exp(ikx)$, it is argued, may “hit” the particle one after another and it is still within Δx . Thus, no momentum distribution is created and one only sees the net effect of $V(x)$ acting within this large Δx .

References

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